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FELLEGI-SUNTER METHOD FOR CONNECTING RECORDS

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ABSTRACT

This scientific article explores the block diagram and key indicators of the Fellegi-Sunter method. The method provides an auxiliary and reliable approach for automated record linkage. The block diagram illustrates the detailed steps of the automated matching process, emphasizing the utilization of the Fellegi-Sunter algorithm.

Keywords: Fellegi-Sunter Method, Record Linkage, Block Diagram, Automated matching, Auxiliary Approach, Probabilistic Record Linkage, Matching Criteria, Key Terms, Data Processing, Data Matching Algorithm, Record Linkage Methodology, Matching Report, Data Integration, Probabilistic Model.

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МЕТОД ФЕЛЛЕГИ-САНТЕРА ДЛЯ СОЕДИНЕНИЯ ЗАПИСЕЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой научной статье исследуется структурная схема и ключевые показатели метода Феллеги-Сантера. Метод обеспечивает вспомогательный и надежный подход для автоматизированной привязки записей. Блок-схема иллюстрирует подробные этапы автоматизированного процесса сопоставления, подчеркивая использование алгоритма Феллеги-Сантера.

Ключевые слова: Метод Феллеги-Сантера, Привязка записей, Блок-схема, Автоматическое сопоставление, Вспомогательный подход, Вероятностная привязка записей, Критерии сопоставления, Ключевые термины, Обработка данных, Алгоритм сопоставления данных, Методология привязки записей, Отчет о сопоставлении, Интеграция данных, Вероятностная модель.

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YOZUVLARNI BOG‘LASH UCHUN FELLEGI-SUNTER USULI

ANNOTATSIYA

ushbu ilmiy maqola Fellegi-Sunter usulining blok diagrammasi va asosiy ko'rsatkichlarini o'rganadi. Usul avtomatlashtirilgan yozuvlarni bog'lash uchun yordamchi va ishonchli yondashuvni ta'minlaydi. Blok diagrammasi Fellegi-Sunter algoritmidan foydalanishni ta'kidlab, avtomatlashtirilgan moslashtirish jarayonining batafsil qadamlarini aks ettiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Fellegi-Sunter usuli, Rekord aloqa, Blok diagrammasi, Avtomatlashtirilgan moslik, Yordamchi yondashuv, Ehtimoliy yozuv aloqasi, Moslik mezonlari, Asosiy shartlari, Ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash, Ma'lumotlarning moslik algoritmi, yozuvlarni bog'lash metodologiyasi, Moslik hisoboti, Ma'lumotlar integratsiyasi, Ehtimol model.

The Fellegi-Sunter method, also known as the probabilistic record linkage method, is a statistical technique used to link records from different data sources to identify and combine records that match the same entity, such as a person or business. This method was introduced in 1969 by Ivan S. Fellegi and Alan B. Sunter.

The Fellegi-Sunter method is a statistical tool used to collect data and separate it into defining elements. This method is widely used in data reporting, data extraction, data validation, and data collection. The process of linking records is important in a variety of fields, including epidemiology, demography, and the social sciences.

This method addresses the challenge of identifying and merging records corresponding to the same entity across datasets. The key components include the comparison of records using attributes, assignment of weights to attributes based on discriminatory power, a probabilistic model to calculate match probabilities, and a decision rule for classification. The approach is flexible, accounting for uncertainties in real-world data, and involves selecting thresholds to balance false positives and false negatives. Additional considerations, such as blocking, the Expectation-Maximization algorithm, and multiple comparisons, contribute to the method's robustness. Overall, the Fellegi-Sunter method plays a crucial role in diverse fields, offering a powerful tool for accurate record linkage amid imperfect and varied datasets.

In doing so, researchers often need to combine or link records from different data sets to conduct comprehensive analyses. We use this method to connect bibliographic information in information-library systems. Of course, we will analyze the association of a person, geographical place name, institution name and other data with a field element in the bibliographic database. If a person is linked by name, literature and information attributed to that author (even if created under a pseudonym) will be provided.

The main purpose of the Fellegi-Sunter method is to check, identify and study the correspondence between several data sets. This method uses the following data for statistical analysis:

- Error rate: Rate of correct data separation by mistake
- Match rate: The percentage of the number of matching data compared to the total number.

This data is a key part of the Fellegi-Sunter method, which helps calculate error and match statistics to identify suitable data.

Here's an overview of the key components of the Fellegi-Sunter method:

Comparison Vector:

Each pair of records is compared using a set of attributes (fields) that are relevant to the linkage process. These attributes might include names, addresses, birth dates, and other identifying information.

Comparison Vector Scores:

For each attribute, a comparison score is assigned based on the level of agreement or disagreement between the values in the compared records. Common scoring methods include exact match, partial match, or no match.

Weights:

Weights are assigned to each attribute based on its discriminatory power. Attributes that are more informative and less prone to errors typically receive higher weights. The weights are often determined through empirical analysis or expert judgment.

Probabilistic Model:

The method uses a probabilistic model to calculate the likelihood that a pair of records represents a match or a non-match. The model considers the comparison scores, weights, and the observed distribution of scores in the data.

Decision Rule:

A decision rule is applied to classify record pairs as matches or non-matches based on the calculated probabilities. This rule involves setting a threshold or cutoff value, above which pairs are considered matches and below which they are considered non-matches.

Classification Results:

The records are then classified into matches and non-matches based on the decision rule. Matches are merged, and the linked dataset is created.

The Fellegi-Sunter method allows for a more flexible and probabilistic approach to record linkage, acknowledging that perfect matches are rare in real-world datasets. It is widely used in various applications, including public health research, census data integration, and social science studies, where accurate linkage of records is essential for meaningful analysis while accounting for uncertainties and errors in the data.

The main elements of the Fellegi-Sunter method are:

- Record: Refers to a collection of data or an array of data.
- Field: Multiple elements or attributes of a data array
- Token: The smallest piece of information, usually a word or number
- Key: A set of data used to determine whether data matches

The structure of the Fellegi-Sunter method includes the following elements:

1. Data strings (records): stored in a data set, table, or file format.
2. Fields (fields): several elements or attributes of a data series. For example, fields for personal data can be name, birthday, address, phone number, e-mail address, gender, etc.
3. Part (token): the smallest part of the information, usually consisting of a word or number. For example, in a row on personal data can consist of such parts as first name, last name, sharif.
4. Keywords for compatibility determination (keys): a set of data used to determine the suitability of data. For example, in one data table, the employee's passport number, id number, phone number and personal data may all be included.

The main purpose of the structure of the Fellegi-Sunter method is to separate the data, determine the suitability of the data and help to verify the data. It is used to illuminate the elements identified in the structure and their corresponding information and to determine their differences from each other.

The algorithm of the Fellegi-Sunter method consists of the following steps:

1. Defining a data string: Defining a data string, for example a table or file format.
2. Identifying Fields and Parts: Identifying each field and parts in a data line. For example, fields for personal information can be name, date of birth, address, phone number, e-mail address, gender, etc.
3. Keywords or match identification: Keywords used to match data, for example, passport number, id number, phone number and personal information may all be included.
4. Determining match statistics: Comparing each piece of data in the dataset against keywords and calculating match and error statistics.
5. Compilation of a set of matches (match set) and a set of non-matches (non-match set): compiling each piece of information in a Data Row into a set of matches by match and a set of matches by match.
6. Evaluation of compatibility and error statistics: determination of a number of values for the evaluation of compatibility and error statistics, these are called Q_u and Q_m .
7. Presentation of Q_u and Q_m values: Q_u and Q_m values help in the process of data separation and detection.
8. Updating compatibility and error statistics: recalculating compatibility and error statistics based on Q_u and Q_m values to update compatibility and error statistics.

9. Presentation of the results according to the requirements: once the data is separated and the suitability is determined, it is possible to draw up and study a report of the suitability and error on the requirements and objectives.

1-block-scheme. Algorithm of Fellegi-Sunter.

The block diagram of the Fellegi-Sunter method appears as follows:

- Retrieve Necessary Data from the Database: Obtain the required information from the database.
- Automated Data Processing and Preparation of Matching Report: Automatically process the data and prepare a matching report.
- Input Key Terms and Matching Criteria: Input key terms and matching criteria required for the matching process.
- Implement the Fellegi-Sunter Algorithm: Execute the Fellegi-Sunter algorithm, which manages the matching process based on key terms and criteria.
- Update Matching Report and Prepare Results Report: Update the matching report with the algorithm's results and prepare an overall results report.
- Input Matching Report Responses into the Database: Input the responses from the matching report into the database.
- Utilize Responses for the Next Iteration of the Fellegi-Sunter Algorithm: Use the responses to inform the next iteration of the Fellegi-Sunter algorithm. This step is often automated.
- Verify the Purpose Suitability of Matching Report Responses Before Re-execution: Prior to re-execution, verify the suitability of matching report responses for the intended purpose.

- Re-execute and Update Matching Report: Re-execute the Fellegi-Sunter algorithm with any necessary adjustments and update the matching report.
- For Highly Automated Processes, Input New Data into the Database Automatically: For processes heavily reliant on automation, new data is automatically input into the database.

This block diagram illustrates a supportive and indicative method for record linkage within the structure of a database. It is particularly useful for automating and streamlining the matching process through a database-driven approach.

The main advantages and challenges of the Fellegi-Sunter method are as follows:

Main Advantages:

Auxiliary and Trustworthy Approach:

The Fellegi-Sunter method operates on a probabilistic basis, providing auxiliary support and a trustworthy approach. It ensures data security and reliability in the context of large-scale databases.

Automation:

The Fellegi-Sunter method allows for automation, making it easier to implement automated reports and streamline the processing of large datasets. This is particularly valuable for efficient data matching and linkage.

Versatility in Applications:

The method's adaptability makes it suitable for various fields. It can be employed in applications ranging from personal information databases to business transactions and beyond.

Challenges and Issues:

Field and Segment Limitations:

The Fellegi-Sunter method requires the use of single fields and segments, which may pose challenges when matching data.

Errors and Data Corrections:

The accuracy of the method may be affected by errors in data, and corrections or modifications in the data can create challenges in the matching process.

Automation of Scoring:

Automating the process of match and mismatch scoring can be challenging. The optimization of Q_u and Q_m values may need manual adjustments to enhance the method's performance.

Proximity of Results and Available Data:

While the Fellegi-Sunter method delivers close results, handling unnoticed errors or specific features may require additional attention.

The effectiveness of using the Fellegi-Sunter method depends on the specific goals and requirements. Understanding the existing challenges, adapting the matching process to local standards, and addressing unnoticed errors can maximize the benefits of this method.

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